

What *is* reasoning anyway? A closer look at reasoning in LLMs

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There is a remarkable degree of polarisation in current debate about the capacities of Large Language Models (LLMs). One example of this is the debate about reasoning. Some researchers see ample evidence of reasoning in these systems, while others maintain that these systems do not reason at all. This paper seeks to shed light on this debate by examining the divergent uses of the term reasoning across different disciplines. It provides a simple clarificatory framework for talking about behaviour that highlights key dimensions of variation in how ‘reasoning’ is used across psychology, philosophy and AI. This highlights not just the extent to which researchers are talking past each other, but also that common inferences about model capability that accompany classification decisions are, in fact, far less compelling than they might seem.

Additional Key Words and Phrases: Large Language Models, reasoning, AI, human reasoning

1 Introduction

There is considerable controversy about the reasoning capabilities of current AI systems. This controversy concerns not just the extent of such systems’ reasoning capabilities, but whether they can be considered to be reasoning at all. Wildly diverging views on this can be found not just in online discourse, blog posts, and the press, but also in published research articles. In particular, extreme disagreement can be found even among researchers with relevant expertise. Even within the AI community, one can find voices who view not just LLMs but also next generation large reasoning models (LRMs) like OpenAI’s o1 and o3 models or DeepSeek’s R1, which are specifically geared toward reasoning, as merely mimicking it [86]. That controversy only widens when one includes researchers from other disciplines. Fig. 1 provides some examples which already make clear that there is no simple explanation for those divergences; by no means, for example, are positive assessments restricted only to researchers directly involved in the design and development of these systems who might be inclined toward ‘hype’ (see e.g., the quote by Thagard, 2024).

The mere fact of that controversy over whether generative AI systems ‘reason’ would merit a closer look. One of the most remarkable features of that controversy, however, is not just that different people come to different overall conclusions, but rather that they seemingly think that their conclusion is obvious. This seems well-illustrated by this recent quote:

“So if ChatGPT is nothing more than souped-up autocomplete, why are so many convinced that it’s actually “understanding” or “reasoning”?” (from Bender & Hanna, The AI Con, 2025)

The question of how such fundamental disagreement is even possible seems an interesting question and one that seems important to understand if debate is to come to meaningful assessments of the capacities of current AI.

The current paper is an attempt to move the debate forward. To this end, it seeks to clarify important variations in the way the word ‘reasoning’ is used both within and across relevant fields. It also seeks to clarify questions about why a decision on whether or not these systems reason even matters; that is, it seeks to identify differences among researchers with respect to the consequences that flow from deciding, one way or the other, whether these systems ‘reason’.

To this end, the paper proceeds in three main parts. The first part brings together definitions and examples of use for the term ‘reasoning’ from ordinary, everyday language, as well as from psychology, philosophy, and AI. Crucially, that review focusses on use and definitions *prior* to the advent of LLMs. The second part introduces a simple conceptual framework for making sense of typical and atypical cases of behaviour; this is then used to help understand cross-disciplinary differences. The third, and final, main part then examines the implications of classification.

<p>AI tools don't think, because they don't <i>need to</i>...AI models use mathematical data structures to mimic the outputs of human intelligence –our acts of reasoning, speech, movement, sensing, and so on (Vallor, 2024)</p>	<p>"..GPT4 is capable of both identifying and using external tools on its own in order to improve performance. It is able to reason about which tools it needs, effectively parse the output of these tools and respond appropriately (i.e., interact with them appropriately), all without any specialised training or fine-tuning." (Bubeck et al., 2023)</p>
<p>"Artificial intelligence is algorithmic mimicry" (Jaeger, 2023)</p>	<p>"our results strongly suggest that LLMs are decent zero-shot reasoners."..." our method is a multi-task prompt and elicits ...broad cognitive abilities in LLMs, such as logical reasoning..." (Kojima et al., 2022)</p>
<p>"So if ChatGPT is nothing more than souped-up autocomplete, why are so many convinced that it's actually "understanding" or "reasoning"?" (Bender & Hanna, The AI Con, 2025)?"</p>	<p>"Causal reasoning seems to be another emergent skill that ChatGPT gains from its training data" (Thagard, 2024, pg. 22)</p>

Fig. 1. Some opposing sample views on the question of whether LLMs reason.

2 What *is* reasoning?

The most basic definition found in dictionaries reduces the meaning of 'reasoning' simply to the act or process of using 'reason' (whatever that may be):

"The use of reason; especially the drawing of inferences or conclusions through the use of reason"
(Merriam-Webster)

Pursuing, then, the question of what an inference is, one is led back to the notion of reasoning:

"inference: reasoning from something known or assumed to something else which follows from it"
(Oxford English Dictionary)

This leaves one only marginally wiser, bar having learned also that the word 'infer' itself derives from the Latin for 'carry forward'. Other dictionary definitions introduce a qualification on the 'process of using reason' that stems from the nature of reason (Latin 'ratio') itself:

"reasoning: the process of thinking about something in a logical way in order to form a conclusion or judgment"
(Britannica)

"Reasoning involves using more-or-less rational processes of thinking and cognition to extrapolate from one's existing knowledge to generate new knowledge"
(Wikipedia)

Clearly this range of everyday definitions already allows for divergent assessments of LLM capacities depending on how one thinks about 'using reason', 'thinking', 'knowing', or 'more-or-less rational', and which of these one's chosen definition requires.

Possibly, greater clarity could, however, be found in the three academic disciplines most concerned with reasoning: psychology, philosophy and artificial intelligence. Closer inspection of how each of these disciplines defines or speaks about reasoning reveals that this is not the case. Each of these disciplines is next discussed in turn.

2.1 How Psychology Speaks About Reasoning

Psychology, as a discipline, is rather adverse to defining its fundamental terms, preferring instead to work with operational definitions that focus on observable outcomes indicative of the underlying construct. I would wager that the majority of psychology papers that use the term reasoning provide no definition at all. The following passage seems illustrative of the way psychologists speak about not just reasoning, but other fundamental concepts like thinking or understanding. For background, the excerpt is the opening passage of a recent high profile review of the psychology of reasoning by Oaksford and Chater (2020), two of the field's leading exponents:

“Psychologists have studied adult verbal reasoning for more than half a century, initially viewing binary logic, in which propositions can only be true or false, as the appropriate standard of correct inference. Typical experiments focus on a small range of verbal inferences using the logical terms of natural language such as and, or, not, if...then, all, some. Participants might be given some premises—for example, if the key is turned, the car starts, and the key is turned—and then asked whether they endorse the conclusion that the car starts. Here, if they are reasoning using classical logic, they should endorse the conclusion.”
(Oaksford & Chater, 2020, pg. 306)

The following features are worth drawing attention to: the opening paragraph focuses on an overt behaviour (adult verbal reasoning) and notes the historical focus of the psychology of reasoning on logic. It then immediately moves to the description of *experimental paradigms* and the conclusions of interest that are drawn from these. No further definition of reasoning is given in the article.

Consideration of other works in the psychology of reasoning (e.g., Wason & Johnson-Laird, 1972) or also educational psychology (Nickerson, 2004) makes clear that, historically, there were multiple notions of reasoning concurrently in use within the literature: a narrow one focussed on logic and deduction and a more general one involving the kinds of processes that subserve activities as diverse as solving puzzles, determining best routes, solving problems, or planning (see Table 1, entries 1 and 2).

In keeping with that breadth, psychology also has multiple research areas focussed on specific (non-logic based) forms of reasoning, from analogical reasoning [42], inductive reasoning [10, 54], moral reasoning [95], causal reasoning [131], to probabilistic reasoning [127], which themselves partially overlap.

Other definitions found in the psychology literature consequently equate reasoning and inference in the manner of some of the dictionary definitions presented above (see Table 1, entries 3 and 4).

One final characteristic of psychologists' use of the term reasoning is that it is explicitly not constrained with respect to the kind of process that underlies that inference. An example of this can be found in the abstract of the widely cited (1996) paper by Sloman “The Empirical Case for Two Systems of Reasoning” (see Table 1, entry 5) which sets out the idea that human cognition involves two distinct systems, one rule-based and one associative, that can simultaneously generate solutions (including rival solutions) to reasoning problems. This maps on to the distinction between ‘System 1’ and ‘System 2’ [37, 121] -see entry 6, Table 1. Such plurality of potential process is not limited to dual-systems views of cognition, however. It is also manifest in the exposition of different computational approaches to the topic –symbolic, connectionist, and symbolic-connectionist– set out by [33] in the Oxford Handbook of Thinking and Reasoning [56]. All of this contrasts rather starkly with the use of the term reasoning in philosophy.

Table 1. Sample definitions and usage from psychology.

Author	Quote
Wason, P. C., & Johnson-Laird, P. N. (1972)	This book is primarily about our own research into the psychology of reasoning. There is, of course, no clear boundary surrounding this topic. It is obvious, for example, that when an individual draws a conclusion from premises according to the traditional Aristotelian laws of logic, he is engaged in reasoning. It is also feasible to assert that an individual solving a crossword puzzle, planning to buy a new house, or determining the best route from one town to another, is also engaged in reasoning.
Nickerson, R. S. (2004)	As used in the psychological literature, reasoning has a variety of connotations that differ in their inclusiveness. At one extreme, the term is used to connote what once was called ratiocination, the process of deductive inferencing. At the other, it encompasses many aspects of thinking, in addition to deduction, that are involved in drawing conclusions, making choices, solving problems, and trying to figure out what to believe.
Bucciarelli, M., Khemlani, S., & Johnson-Laird, P. N. (2008)	Reasoning or inference – we use the terms inter-changeably – is any systematic mental process that constructs or evaluates implications from premises of some sort. Implications are either deductive or inductive...
Leighton, J. P., & Sternberg, R. J. (Eds.). (2004)	Defining Reasoning. In the present book, reasoning is broadly defined as the process of drawing conclusions. Moreover, these conclusions inform problem-solving and decision-making endeavours ...
Kurtz, K. J., Gentner, D., & Gunn, V. (1999)	This chapter focuses on the concept of human reasoning that can be broadly described as a set of cognitive processes by which people take an initial set of information and generate inferences that extend beyond the original data.
Slovan, S. A. (1996)	Distinctions have been proposed between systems of reasoning for centuries. This article distills properties shared by many of these distinctions and characterizes the resulting systems in light of recent findings and theoretical developments. One system is associative because its computations reflect similarity structure and relations of temporal contiguity. The other is "rule based" because it operates on symbolic structures that have logical content and variables and because its computations have the properties that are normally assigned to rules. The systems serve complementary functions and can simultaneously generate different solutions to a reasoning problem. The rule-based system can suppress the associative system but not completely inhibit it. The article reviews evidence in favor of the distinction and its characterization.
Evans, J. S. B. (2003)	Researchers in thinking and reasoning have proposed recently that there are two distinct cognitive systems underlying reasoning. System 1 is old in evolutionary terms and shared with other animals: it comprises a set of autonomous subsystems that include both innate input modules and domain-specific knowledge acquired by a domain-general learning mechanism. System 2 is evolutionarily recent and distinctively human: it permits abstract reasoning and hypothetical thinking, but is constrained by working memory capacity and correlated with measures of general intelligence. These theories essentially posit two minds in one brain with a range of experimental psychological evidence showing that the two systems compete for control of our inferences and actions.
Sniderman, P. M., Brody, R. A., & Tetlock, P. E. (1991)	In contrast, the argument of this book is that ordinary people do reason through their choices over a range of issues. By reason, we do not mean self-conscious acts of cerebration, merely that people can occasionally take advantage of shortcuts in judgment to figure out dependably what they favor politically.

2.2 Philosophy

“There is a tendency to identify reasoning with proof or argument in accordance with rules of logic...But... Reasoning is not argument or proof. It is a procedure for revising one’s beliefs, for changing one’s view.” (Harman, 1984, pg. 107)

The idea that reasoning is about belief revision can be found in multiple works in philosophy [16, 84], but ‘good reasoning’ is not necessarily equated with (just) logic, see entry 1, Table 2. Rather, at its most general, reasoning is a functional kind whose aim is to fix ‘fitting attitudes’, that is, it is aimed simply at ‘getting things right’[84].

In this, it is widely assumed (e.g., [16, 17, 84], but see [128]) that reasoning consists of *rule-following*, in particular, formal rules of some sort (e.g., modus ponens). In other words, the behaviour of the cognitive system is not merely describable by rules (as are, for example the orbits of planets in the solar system), but rather it is rule-guided (a representation of one or more inference rules plays a causal role in the behaviour of the system, on rule-following vs. rule-describable behaviour more generally, see e.g.,[47]).

Crucially, in stark contrast to psychology, the restriction of ‘reasoning’ to processes that are subject to conscious awareness seems near universal in philosophy (for an exception see [69]). For example:

“First, by ‘reasoning’ we mean personal-level, conscious, active reasoning. We do not mean subpersonal, unconscious, or automatic information-processing. As Boghossian (2014) puts it, making reference to the well-known distinction between ‘System 1’ and ‘System 2’ processes, reasoning in our sense is ‘System 1.5 and up’ (p. 2). Second, although it is convenient to represent bits of reasoning in the way that you might express them in language, as above, we don’t assume that reasoning requires you to engage in speech, inner or outer. Third, as our examples indicate, we will discuss not only theoretical reasoning (reasoning to beliefs) but also practical reasoning (reasoning to intentions). We take there to be good grounds for supposing that reasoning is at some level a unified phenomenon.” pg. 168

A further distinction drawn in the philosophy literature is between ‘internal’ and ‘external’ accounts of reasoning, where the latter refers to a notion of ‘reason with someone’ (as in ‘he can’t be reasoned with’) [73] (see McKenzie, 1989 in Table 2). This, in turn, is paralleled in the discussion about the relationship of reasoning to both inference and argument[132]. While some definitions have largely equate inference and reasoning or inference and argument (see Runes, 1984, Table 2), many others view them as distinct because they see ‘argument’ as public (see Govier, 1989, Table 2) or as lacking the agent-internal aspect of belief change (e.g., [49, 50]).

Finally, there is the (somewhat opaque) related notion of ‘standing in the space of reasons’[14, 83, 115]. This notion is part of attempts to elucidate the nature of knowledge, and, as such, is not immediately about reasoning per se. To the extent that it involves the notion of ‘having reasons’ for one’s actions or beliefs, it is however, bound up with questions about inference and has featured both in discussion about whether (non-human) animal action [57] and LLMs [53, 76, 109] can stand in the space of reason.

2.3 Artificial Intelligence

Artificial Intelligence, our third discipline of interest, has used the term reasoning since the early days of the field. Moreover, like psychology, it has pursued many different types of reasoning: logical reasoning [80], theorem proving [71], default reasoning [101], case-based reasoning [62], probabilistic reasoning [96], abductive reasoning [94], common sense reasoning [31] and so on.

In fact, the Dictionary of Computer Science (1976/2003) contains no definition of reasoning and has entries only for specific kinds of reasoning, see entries 1-3, Table 3. Similarly, the core textbook in the field, Russell & Norvig (2021) [108] contains hundreds of mentions of the word ‘reasoning’, across a thousand pages, but, again, no definition.

Table 2. Sample definitions and usage from philosophy.

Author	Quote
McHugh & Way, 2018	“Reasoning is a certain kind of attitude-revision. What kind? The aim of this paper is to introduce and defend a new answer to this question, based on the idea that reasoning is a goodness-fixing kind. Our central claim is that reasoning is a functional kind: it has a constitutive point or aim that fixes the standards for good reasoning. We claim, further, that this aim is to get fitting attitudes.”
Valaris, 2017	“According to many, reasoning is fundamentally a matter of <i>following rules</i> . This is not just the relatively innocuous claim that reasoning (or at least good reasoning) can be described or captured by rules. It is the stronger claim that our subject gets to know that Socrates is mortal in virtue of being guided by, or following, a rule—a mental analogue of the rule of modus ponens familiar from propositional logic.”
Broome, 2013	“Active reasoning is a particular sort of process by which conscious premise-attitudes cause you to acquire a conclusion-attitude. The process is that you operate on the contents of your premise-attitudes following a rule, to construct the conclusion, which is the content of a new attitude of yours that you acquire in the process.”
McKenzie, 1989	“Various kinds of processes are called reasoning. Most of them fall into one of two groups, the internal or mental, and the external or social. ‘Reason’ is to be construed internally in contexts like ‘I got the answer by reasoning it out for myself’, ‘Use the power to reason that the Good gave you’. In describing these uses as mental, I am not of course ruling out the possibility that some further account of the mental can be given in turn. Where reason is taken to be mental, it is taken to be a process which goes on within a single human being, like the feeling of anger or the feeling of affection. On the other hand, ‘reason’ is to be construed externally in contexts like ‘You just can’t reason with him’, ‘Perhaps we can resolve this by bringing the parties together and reasoning with them’. Here the process of reasoning is being regarded as a kind of interaction between people, as boxing and lovemaking are. It is taken to be a social phenomenon.”
Runes, 1984	“Reasoning is the process of inference; it is the process of passing from certain propositions already known or assumed to be true, to another truth distinct from them but following from them; it is a discourse or argument which infers one proposition from another, or from a group of others having some common elements between them” (ibid., p. 281).
Govier, 1989	“An argument is a publicly expressed tool of persuasion. Typically it takes thinking to construct an argument. Reasoning is distinguished from arguing along these lines: reasoning is what you may do before you argue, and your argument expresses some of your (best) reasoning. But much reasoning is done before and outside the context of argument” (ibid., p. 117).

Table 3. Sample definitions and usage from AI.

Author	Quote
Encyclopedia of Computer Science, 1976	“The study of certain theoretical questions about processes of reasoning by computer (performing deductions, forming hypotheses, using knowledge effectively in problem-solving processes) is beginning to create points of contact between certain parts of philosophy (logic, epistemology, methodology) and computer science.”
Encyclopedia of Computer Science, 2003	Nine major branches of theory have been developed for artificial intelligence. (1) Logic systems for mechanical reasoning such as first-order logic, fuzzy logic, temporal logic, nonmonotonic logic, probabilistic logic, deduction, and induction. (pg. 149)
Encyclopedia of Computer Science, 2003	“Problem-solving models include case-based reasoning, qualitative reasoning, constraint-based and opportunistic reasoning, distributed and cooperative reasoning, and nonlinear planning.” (pg. 149)
Davis, 2023	“Since Turing, the consensus in the AI community has been that the capacities of an AI system, such as intelligence, reasoning, and knowledge, are determined by the tasks it can carry out, regardless of the internal architecture. In particular, an AI possesses commonsense knowledge if it can succeed at tasks that require common sense.”

However, the following passage gives an impression of how the term is used:

“One quick way to summarize the milestones in AI history is to list the Turing Award winners: Marvin Minsky (1969) and John McCarthy (1971) for defining the foundations of the field based on representation and reasoning; Ed Feigenbaum and Raj Reddy (1994) for developing expert systems that encode human knowledge to solve real-world problems; Judea Pearl (2011) for developing probabilistic reasoning techniques that deal with uncertainty in a principled manner; and finally Yoshua Bengio, Geoffrey Hinton, and Yann LeCun (2019) for making “deep learning” (multilayer neural networks) a critical part of modern computing

The picture that emerges from passages such as this and others is that something qualifies as ‘reasoning’ because it utilizes a standard formal system for inference (e.g., deduction, Bayesian conditioning) –regardless of the overall task the system is trying to address. Additionally, it may be characterised as reasoning because it involves formal tools or algorithms specifically designed as alternatives or extensions to those standard formal systems (e.g., default reasoning, case-based reasoning, ‘argumentation’ as an approach to non-monotonic reasoning).

What is typically *not* intended by the use of the term ‘reasoning’ in AI is any strong claim about corresponding to what it is that humans do (see entries, Table 3). Since [113], AI researchers have distinguished between “strong AI” and “weak AI”. On Searle’s definition, “weak AI” views computer programs simply as a tool for studying the human mind. According to “strong AI”, by contrast, “the appropriately programmed computer really *is* a mind, in the sense that computers given the right programs can be literally said to understand and have other cognitive states” ([113], pg. 417).

Weak AI consequently refers simply to domain-specific algorithms for tasks that would be considered intelligent if carried out by humans (see also [13]). And, to the extent that AI became a field of study and a research programme,

it covered *attempts* to build such systems. In short, the term ‘reasoning’ was used not only to characterise systems that achieved human levels of competence on those tasks, but also systems that were both highly limited in scope, and considerably fell short of human performance in that domain.

By the same token, what, historically at least, was explicitly disavowed is any sense that ‘reasoning’ involves consciousness. This is apparent in Russell and Norvig’s textbook in its short section on “Can Machines Really Think?” and the limits of AI. This section equates ‘thinking’ with ‘consciously thinking’, and makes clear that they think no system has achieved that to date, while also declaring the question to be uninteresting. With the latter they affirm a tradition in AI that goes all the way back to Turing [126].

By contrast, the advent of LLMs and the quest for ‘Artificial General Intelligence’ (AGI) has now prompted articles on issues such as whether LLMs might be ‘sentient’ [2]; this conceivably could start to shift the meaning of reasoning (at least if there were any meaningful evidence for LLM sentience, for critical appraisals see [23, 35]), but that does not alter the fact that the term ‘reasoning’ has been used in AI for decades without any implication of conscious awareness.

Needless to say, LLMs may change AI’s notion of reasoning as is apparent in recent attempts to define reasoning specifically for the purpose of evaluating LLMs[40]:

“The definition of reasoning in modern AI systems remains an evolving construct, particularly within the context of LLMs exemplified by DeepSeek R1 and OpenAI O1. Here, under the scope of LLMs, we formalize reasoning as a structured, multi-step process that dynamically decomposes complex problems, generates intermediate hypotheses, and iteratively refines solutions through logical and evidence-based transformations.”

Under that characterisation, ‘reasoning’ is a teleological, multi-step process that, generates new knowledge or facts. Again, what it is not, is something that needs to be tied to the way humans do things, let alone needs to be conscious (see also, e.g.,[70]).

Finally, it is important to note that ‘reasoning’ in AI systems is not some distant, future prospect, but –in the view of the field itself– something many AI systems have already successfully exhibited. The open question is simply whether LLMs, specifically, can likewise do so.

3 Resolving the Confusion

It is clear from the preceding survey that there is within-discipline variation in the meaning of ‘reasoning’-variation that requires understanding of context to resolve. Additionally, there is significant systematic variation across disciplines. In light of that, it seems inevitable that current debate on whether or not LLMs ‘reason’ likely involves considerable amounts of talking past one another.

This makes it desirable to clarify the notion of reasoning further and find ways of speaking about it that draw out clearly the underlying matters of disagreement, rather than obscuring them with a terminological Tower of Babel. In order to promote such clarification, the next section introduces a new, simple framework for talking about reasoning in the context of human and non-human agents. To this end, it takes a step back and identifies a more general difficulty that arises with classification and debate concerning human behaviour.

4 An underlying difficulty in characterising behaviour

On reflection, there seems to be something particularly confusing about words that describe human behaviour or human activity that already affects words for everyday actions like ‘read’, ‘walk’, ‘climb’, or ‘talk’, and not just difficult concepts like ‘understand’, ‘think’, or ‘reason’. Specifically, there is confusion that can arise from the fact that we can think about human behaviour along three different dimensions: task, means, and attainment.

For example, when talking about ‘reading’ and considering whether a particular child is reading, we could be concerned with, or focussed on: 1) *a task*, in the case of reading something like ‘extracting meaning from written

text’, or 2) *the means* by which performance on that task is achieved –say, ‘sounding out letters’ versus ‘whole word recognition’, or 3) *attainment*, that is, how well the child reads, say first grade, 6th grade, or adult level.

A *typical case* of behaviour is typical along *all three dimensions*. Moving away from such prototypical cases along any one of these dimensions can raise questions about word boundaries. To carry on with the example of reading, we could find ourselves variously saying something like:

- (1) “he can’t really read yet, he’s still painstakingly sounding out each word” (attainment too low)
- (2) “he didn’t really read what I said, he just responded to the tone” (not the same task)
- (3) “he’s not really reading, he seems to have simply memorised entire passages” (different means).

In short, we can think of these three aspects –tasks, means, attainment– as setting out the axes of a three dimensional space in which to locate typical and atypical cases of a behaviour like reading.¹ This space is illustrated in Figure 2. We can think of typical cases as occupying a central position in that space, while atypical cases deviate from those typical cases on one or more dimensions. As always, the task of classifying those atypical cases can be thought of as deciding where in the space to place the category boundaries [90].

This conceptual framework can equally be applied to a behaviour like ‘logical reasoning’. One might construe an unproblematic case of logical reasoning by a human as follows:

- *Task*: derives a conclusion that follows deductively from the premises
- *Attainment*: only (or mostly) derives deductively valid conclusions from given premises
- *Means*: uses a set of inference rules (e.g., a natural deduction system) or makes use of model checking (e.g., uses truth tables)

In the history of the psychology of reasoning surveyed in the Oaksford and Chater (2020) review quoted above, each of these aspects were questioned over time. First, a sizeable experimental literature found systematic reasoning failures, given the standards of classical logic. The most well known of these outside of psychology is probably the Wason selection task [133] which finds people systematically selecting the wrong information in order to test a conditional rule (e.g., ‘if a card is red, it has a vowel on the back’). These findings eventually led to the rejection of the idea that human performance on those experimental tasks of logical reasoning was based on participants utilising mental inference rules in the way that had been predicted by the hypothesis that lay logical reasoning was akin to proof in a natural deduction system[104] (the hypothesis that people might be manipulating models to conduct such inference has been more enduring, but even among proponents of ‘mental models’ theory, those models and checking procedures no longer look like scrutinising truth tables [60]). This, finally, led to the realisation that participants’ behaviour might better be understood as viewing the task in a different light [91]. If one took participants to be engaging in probabilistic reasoning instead, data patterns of seeming logical reasoning failures could be explained. What looked like patterns of logical failure showed themselves to be compatible with probabilistic success. This then prompted the probabilistic turn the psychology of reasoning took, that is, the shift to the ‘new paradigm in the psychology of reasoning’ that Oaksford and Chater’s (2020) review surveys.

This example illustrates that the framework can be used to articulate concisely the trajectory of a particular field concerned with understanding human reasoning. It illustrates also that while the individual dimensions are conceptually separable, and distinguishing them adds conceptual clarity, we routinely draw inferences across these dimensions –as illustrated in Fig. 3. In the simple reading example, realising that someone has access only to inferior means (rote memorisation) will allow us to predict contexts where their attainment will be low. The same kinds of inferences are routinely drawn in the scientific study of human behaviour and the history of the psychology of reasoning provides just one example. These bi-directional cross-dimensional inferences (see Fig. 3) are possible because the three conceptually distinct aspects of behaviour constrain one another in practice.

¹The basic idea of this 3D space was first described in a blog post. The clarificatory use to which it was put there concerned other aspects of debate over LLMs, see <https://write.as/ulrikehahn/do-llms-really-reason-understand-think-summarise>.

Fig. 2. Dimensions for classifying behaviour.

A particular means may or may not support a candidate task, and, even if it does, it may allow only limited attainment. In other words, for a given behaviour not all regions of space will be realisable; some combinations of task, attainment, and means will not be possible in practice.

Having shown how the conceptual framework of this 3D space might be useful, the remaining sections will apply it to clarify and move forward the current debate about reasoning and LLMs. First is the use of the framework to position the different uses of the term reasoning surveyed above. This will then be followed, in the final section, with its application to particular verdicts on whether or not LLMs reason, that is, specific classification decisions.

5 Applying the framework

The 3D framework can be applied to highlight the differences between disciplines that emerged in our survey above. Specifically, thinking about those differences suggests that each of the three disciplines give these dimensions very different weight in how they determine the category boundaries. In the context of spatial models of similarity-based classification, one can think of the notion of giving a particular dimension more or less weight as stretching

Fig. 3. Cross dimensional inference in the psychological study of logical reasoning.

or shrinking the space along that dimension [90]. Stretching a dimension will render nearby points further apart; shrinking it will bring them further together. This alters the contribution distance along that dimension makes to the overall distance between typical and atypical items.

For psychology, the survey of Section 2.1 made clear that the discipline places a lot of emphasis on ‘task’, adopting operational definitions, while caring little about ‘means’ in its definitions of reasoning, see Fig. 4.a. Whether a behaviour is produced by System 1 or System 2, whether the underlying systems is rule-based or associative, or whether it is best understood in terms of symbolic or connectist computations, is –in first instance– immaterial to whether that behaviour is defined as ‘reasoning’ or not.

This focus makes sense in as much as the ‘means’ are typically what psychologists consider to be unknown and the very thing their discipline is trying to understand. So it makes sense that (unknown) ‘means’ are not core to definition and that psychology’s use of the term reasoning downplays means almost to the point of ignoring means for purposes of classification. The one exception the discipline makes, here, are obviously inappropriate and or inadequate means such as cheating or ‘Clever Hans’ [110] strategies that rest on criteria without meaningful connection with the target behaviour beyond the context of a specific experimental set up or test.

How psychology deals with such cases can be seen in the context of studies of animal cognition and developmental psychology where the possibility of such limited strategies arises regularly. Pigeons, for example, have been shown to ‘learn to distinguish’ images of Monet and Degas [135], though what it is they are doing to make that distinction almost certainly differs from humans. Even in such contexts, psychologists would likely talk as if granting the task (‘pigeons discriminate’) even though the means are quite different (say, pigeons respond to an artist-typical colour spectrum) while acknowledging the difference in means. They would likely resist granting the task only when the means seem extraneous to the ‘task’ as naturally conceived (say, ‘the Monet images all

have more red pixels in the bottom right corner') or are wholly artefactual (say, 'all the Monet images, but none of the Degas, had water marks'). So not only have psychologists long faced some of the issues that arise in the context of trying to evaluate LLMs (see also [66]), much of the skill of being an experimental psychologist consists in designing tasks to probe the nature of such alternative means while also ruling out uninteresting artefacts.

It is likewise understandable that psychological definitions of reasoning downplay the dimension of attainment. Psychologists routinely not only study capacities with respect to both phylogenetic and ontogenetic development, that is across species and across the lifespan, the discipline also has a long standing interest in individual differences. This makes it natural that psychological definitions of capacities would avoid setting attainment thresholds and place little emphasis on attainment overall. As should be clear from the preceding section on cross-dimension inference, that does not mean that psychologists are not acutely interested in gauging attainment, or routinely use it as an inferential cue; it is merely to note that level of attainment, in and of itself, is not given much weight in whether psychologists label something as 'reasoning' or not.

By contrast, philosophical usage of the term reasoning as seen in section 2.2 seems to not only focus on all three dimensions, but 'means', in particular, seem definitionally central to most authors. To say that only conscious, explicit processing can constitute reasoning is to draw a sharp category boundary in the conceptual space (Fig. 4.b) where psychology sees none. Furthermore, philosophy does so by demanding a feature (consciousness) that psychology typically doesn't even care about: The vast majority of research articles on 'reasoning' (across all types of reasoning) in psychology make no mention of consciousness whatsoever. The majority of work on reasoning in psychology is wholly agnostic about the extent to which the psychological processes it seeks to uncover –the means– are introspectively accessible to reasoners or not. The closest reasoning researchers might come to any consideration of conscious awareness is through methods such as think aloud protocols [36]. Even here, there is a history of research showing that the content of self-reported thoughts may bear little resemblance to what participants were actually doing [138] that complicates the use of this methodology. There is even a serious (albeit controversial) perspective on human cognition that draws on a wealth of empirical data to set out the view that the contents of our awareness (whether these be percepts, beliefs or preferences) are not a window into underlying processes but an improvised, confabulation [24].

For Artificial Intelligence, finally, the discussion of use in section 2.3 above suggests a bi-modal approach to classification, see Fig. 4.c. A system can be described as 'reasoning' by virtue of it is using an established formalism for reasoning or one of the frameworks designed specifically to augment or replace those formalisms. As a result, that classification rests virtually exclusively on means, regardless of the specific task the system is trying to achieve. However, research in AI would also describe as 'reasoning' a computational system that approximates the results of those formalisms on what are naturally seen as 'reasoning tasks' even where that system makes no direct use of the formalism. In other words, one can also speak of a non-symbolic, connectionist model that can deal with some fragment of logic as 'reasoning' even where no logical formalisms feature in the programming of the model. This is seen both in older work (e.g., [97, 106]) and in more recent work, for example, on knowledge-graph embedding [3].

The dimension that has, arguably, been of less concern to AI with respect to classification (at least historically) is attainment; this, once again, seems natural given that AI research, for most of its history, only produced systems that could operate in very specialised domains, and more often than not just in restricted (toy versions) thereof.

5.1 Summary

In short, positioning the discourse on reasoning within psychology, philosophy, and AI, respectively, within a three dimensional space of task, means and attainment further clarifies the systematic differences between these disciplines. Furthermore, it becomes apparent how the differences in emphasis across these disciplines naturally reflect their specific disciplinary goals and constraints.

Fig. 4. Characterising the respective uses of ‘reasoning’ across psychology (Panel a), philosophy (Panel B), and AI (Panel C) in terms of the 3D space of task, means, and attainment.

5.2 Moving the debate forward

So far, we have clarified how and why researchers can be talking past each other when using the term ‘reasoning’. Greater awareness of this, in and of itself, should improve discourse, but we might also wish to work toward better, shared, definitions. As has already become apparent, definitions and decisions about category boundaries are goal and context dependent. Words are tools, and whatever distinctions we end up drawing need to be relevant and useful.

Whether our target concept is ‘reasoning’ or whether it is ‘marriage’, trying to decide where the category boundary lies is pointless without consideration of the specific context in which one wants to draw a distinction. Word meanings are ultimately a matter of convention, and those conventions can and do change. Furthermore, actually drawing a hard category boundary will often leave unresolved much of what motivated us to care: The moment we decide that the thing of concern now falls beyond our newly precise boundary, the question simply shifts to ‘it’s not X, but is it similar enough that we nevertheless need to treat it the same as X?’. In other words, just drawing a boundary is unlikely to resolve fully our wider practical and theoretical concerns. This seems directly relevant to current debate about LLMs and reasoning as consideration of that wider context will reveal.

5.3 Implications of Classification

Closer scrutiny of statements about reasoning and LLMs suggests that much of the interest in the debate concerns the kinds of cross-dimensional inferences described in Fig. 3. In particular, many of the statements that can be found that deny that LLMs reason seem to be made in the context of wider discussion about what these systems can or could ever do, that is, in discussion about possible attainment. The most well-known example of this kind is the notion of LLMs as ‘stochastic parrots’ [6]. There the fact that LLMs lack access to ‘situationally embedded meaning’ is used to argue that LLM text output is literally meaningless, and that whatever meaning we attribute it, is meaning that we as users impute. Likewise the above quote by Bender and Hanna that describes ChatGPT as ‘souped-up autocomplete’ comes from a wider response to the undeniable hype cycle currently surrounding generative AI.

Cast in the framework of the 3D behaviour space, these are arguments saying ‘it’s not really reasoning’ given the *means* while simultaneously highlighting these (putatively inadequate) means as predictive of *attainment*.

In fact, most of the skeptical stances on whether or not LLMs ‘reason’ seem to focus primarily on consideration of means, and most of these ‘LLMs can’t reason’ assessments seem tied up with an interest in attainment, that is, with the performance implications of LLMs, see Fig. 5. To say, for example, that LLMs only ‘mimic’ human

reasoning is precisely to say that LLMs don't actually reason, but instead create the appearance of reasoning *by some other means*.

Fig. 5. Examples of classifications driven by a focus on (deficient) means.

What seems surprising about some of these arguments from means is the limited elaboration they typically receive. The exasperation in Bender and Hanna's (2025) quote (i.e., why *are* so many convinced it's actually reasoning?) comes with a sense that these are arguments so powerful that their conclusions are basically self-explanatory. From other vantage points and disciplinary backgrounds, however, these arguments seem far less compelling and the gulf between those competing assessments rests on more than just divergent definitions. The next sections seek to clarify this further.

5.4 Scrutinising popular arguments from means

5.4.1 Lack of meaning. Bender et al.'s [6] trenchant critique of LLMs (and prescient warning of some of the emerging risks) maintains that LLMs do not 'perform natural language understanding' and consequently succeed only "in tasks that can be approached by manipulating linguistic form" (pg. 610) giving rise to the metaphor of the stochastic parrot. It reiterates a point first made in Bender and Koller [8] that languages are pairings of form and meaning, but because the training data for LLMs includes only form, LLMs do not have access to meaning, just statistical relationships (pg. 615). In particular, discourse with LLMs does not involve the co-creation of meaning as can be found in genuine human exchange:

“Text generated by an LM is not grounded in communicative intent, any model of the world, or any model of the reader’s state of mind. It can’t have been, because the training data never included sharing thoughts with a listener, nor does the machine have the ability to do that.”

It is undoubtedly true that part of human language use is the ability to co-create meaning, including the development of new linguistic signs themselves [27, 52]. It is also reasonable to assume that this ability to co-create meaning might be missing in LLMs. Given that, arguably, no known artificial systems possesses the human ability to negotiate meaning, however, it is somewhat unclear why the lack of this particular ability should constitute quite such a fundamental limitation to what these systems could do.

First, the claim that LLMs have access only to form, not meaning, and that this significantly limits their possible attainment seems surprising in light of sizeable research literatures that explored statistical relationships in the context of meaning, considering them not just as some poorly correlated stand-in for meaning, but as part of both *how* we come to know the meanings of words [65, 72, 100] and *what* we come to know when acquiring meanings of words [29] and did so long before the advent of LLMs. Against that background, it is by no means obvious that LLMs lack access to meaning and it is not surprising that multiple authors have conducted detailed analyses that attribute to LLMs core aspects of meaning and, in particular, have concluded that the words occurring in the linguistic output of LLMs genuinely refer [51, 75, 87].

However, more surprising is the sense that ‘lack of situationally embedded meaning’ provides a powerful cap on attainment. One can grant that LLMs will miss some adaptive aspects of human communication skill, but why that would significantly curtail their ability on other tasks, including other tasks like reasoning is not obvious.

Specifically, *no* computational device or programme (outside the world of robotics) that has been built to date has had ‘access to situationally embedded meaning’ in the sense described in the quote. Given that this has not stopped the creation of a wealth of genuinely useful computational tools, it is not entirely clear why this absence would be so damning for LLMs.²

The point about the restriction to form-based aspects of language seems surprising in light of the fact that it is the essence of computation (at least as traditionally conceived) that what manipulation of representation takes place in the course of computation does so with respect to form (i.e., computation is syntactic). To consider a paradigmatic computational device: A pocket calculator does not have a grasp of meaning. There is no sense in which it understands that $1+1 = 2$. Of course, its utility as a computational device rests on the fact that there is, ultimately, a semantic mapping between its physical states and mathematical relationships. Crucially, however, that mapping is not internal to the calculator nor is it in any way accessible to it.

Needless to say, the syntactic nature of computation has prompted a long history of critique [34, 113], and counter-critiques [28, 102] with respect to the computational metaphor as a suitable framework for understanding the mind. Those foundational theoretical debates aside, however, every natural language processing system built to date has manipulated meaning only via aspects of form. The same is true of all of reasoning systems developed over the history of AI.

5.4.2 Souped-up auto-complete. Seemingly equally obvious is that ‘souped up auto-complete’ (i.e., next token prediction) forms a wholly inadequate computational basis for anything one might deem ‘reasoning’. However, that perspective seems at odds with sizeable research literatures that predate LLMs. In particular, it seems at odds with the fact that, within cognitive neuroscience, predictive coding constitutes a candidate hypothesis for fundamental explanations of the way brains function. Here, the idea is that the brain is continuously trying to predict environmental inputs by maintaining a generative model that is refined and updated by minimising prediction error [26]. Furthermore, not only is this an active hypothesis in trying to comprehend the brain, this

²For wider elaboration of this point see <https://write.as/ulrikehahn/stochastic-parrot-is-a-misleading-metaphor-for-llms>.

hypothesis also has explicit links to the history and development of LLMs as third generation connectionist models [55, 93, 120].

Again, as with the putative lack of meaning, predictive coding may or may not turn out to be an adequate mechanism for high-levels of attainment in LLMs, but the question of whether it actually will seems non-obvious in light of that research literature.

5.4.3 Vallor’s argument for mimicry. A similar sense of seeming obviousness surrounds Vallor’s dismissal of LLMs [129] as genuinely thinking or reasoning. Her claim that LLMs only mimic such behaviours rests on two closely related points, concerning the relationship between minds and brains. The first is the argument from supervenience:

“most of us accept that minds are in some way supervenient on the physical brain. That is, minds depend upon the brain for their reality. Minds are unlikely to be free-floating intangibles...”

In the same context, Vallor then argues that minds “almost certainly come into existence *through* the body and its physical operations” in such a way that it is not just our brains but other bodily systems that affect the mind: “Our minds are *embodied* rather than just connected or contained by our bodies.”

These arguments are not unpacked any further in Vallor’s book, but closer scrutiny makes the claim of widespread consensus seem problematic. There is, indeed, a widespread view that minds ‘supervene’ on brains, though the notion of supervenience itself is also subject to extensive debate. Specifically, the notion of supervenience is an attempt to formulate a particular kind of relationship of necessary dependence:

“A set of properties A supervenes upon another set B just in case no two things can differ with respect to A-properties without also differing with respect to their B-properties. In slogan form, “there cannot be an A-difference without a B-difference.”[85]

While there is debate on the exact nature of that dependence (logical, metaphysical, by virtue of the laws of nature etc.), to say that the mind supervenes on the brain is to say that there cannot be differences in mental states without differences in brain states.

The reverse, however, is *not* implied: different brain states may correspond to the same mental state. Supervenience is fundamentally non-symmetric. Nor is the relationship a causal one. For these reasons, the notion of supervenience very much does not imply that *only* brains can give rise to minds. But that is precisely the question at issue when we ask whether current AI systems ‘think’ or ‘reason’. So supervenience, even where granted, simply does not answer that question.

In fact, functionalism, in its various forms, has held that what makes something a mental state is simply its role or function within the system [68], and the motivation for that view came, in good part, from the sense that agents very different to us could, in principle, have the capacity to reason or think. The discussion around functionalism within philosophy and the various aspects of mental states that it might not capture (such as qualia, the subjective properties of conscious experience [12], or a sense of ‘knowing what it is like’ to have a particular type of experience [88]) has been extensive precisely because functionalism was long the dominant view. It may or may not be the best view of the mental we can come up with, but the claim that there is consensus that minds require brains seems somewhat misleading in light of it. At the very least it must be acknowledged that these issues go to the heart of one of the most long-running and seemingly intractable debates humans have had, namely ‘how, exactly, is the mental related to the physical?’.

That should also make clear that the question of supervenience is distinct from debates about ‘embodiment’. The latter is an issue with a long and important history both in critiques of AI [15] and in cognitive psychology [4, 139]. In both cases, embodiment was historically leveraged as an argument against the sufficiency of a-modal symbols as a comprehensive basis for cognition. Ironically, such a-model symbols are not the kinds of representations and algorithmic processes that LLMs are built around, and it is precisely the putative absence of ‘symbolic processing’

that critics such as Marcus wish to draw on in order to deny ‘true reasoning abilities’ in these systems [5, 67, 77] and have ventured against connectionist systems for decades (e.g., [38, 78], but see [48, 81, 118]).

Furthermore, it is one thing to claim, with good empirical basis, that human thinking and reasoning carries traces of embodiment, but quite another to establish that reasoning and thinking can *only* happen in human-like embodied brains. The latter, however, is the actual question posed by current LLMs.

Here, it is worth remembering why thinking and reasoning seem much less inherently tied to embodiment than other aspects of cognition: Reasoning fundamentally involves a transition between information states. Reasoning as a process, of course, must have some physical manifestation. However, that process is not typically what we consider to be important. This is seen nowhere more clearly than in the fact that our *standards* for reasoning, whether these be logic, probability theory, or decision theory, solely evaluate relationships between information states, which is precisely why these normative frameworks are seen as formal and algorithmic [45]. This makes reasoning quite different to an activity like ‘jumping’, whose ‘goodness’ we evaluate in physical terms (e.g., how high? how far?). This characteristic of reasoning manifests in the contrast to other cognitive processes as well: Unlike, say, percepts, a ‘reason’ can be readily detached from the process of reasoning, as we routinely do when we communicate them.

As we also saw in earlier in this paper, the normative standards by which we evaluate reasoning are not gratuitous, external viewpoints that we may, or may not, bring to ‘reasoning’; rather, on at least some views, meeting such normative standards is seen as constitutive of what it means to ‘reason’ in the first place. At a minimum, then, it requires additional explanation why a process whose relevant output is in important ways non-physical would necessarily require a particular kind of physical substrate. It is one thing to posit that a process whose outputs we evaluate in physical terms has strong physical constraints -say ‘baking’ and ‘cake’. It is quite another to posit the same for ‘reasoning’ and ‘reasons’.

5.4.4 The common thread. The common thread uniting the means discussed in this section is that whatever limited means LLMs have (lack of situationally embedded meaning, next token prediction, lack of embodiment), and what they do as a result, is (supposedly) completely different to what humans draw on. While the section has described relevant considerations and debates concerning these arguments individually, these different arguments share a more fundamental problem. In effect, they are all arguments from means to attainment. Such inference faces a number of general problems, regardless of the specific ‘means’ under consideration. These problems are discussed next.

5.4.5 The gap to cognitive science. Thus far, we have discussed ways in which prominent arguments seeking to deny that current generative AI systems have a capacity for reasoning seem to overlook relevant bodies of research within cognitive science. In particular, they seem to overlook various ways in which computational explanation of human reasoning has been deemed fruitful and plausible in the past, long prior to, and independently of, these models. However, cognitive science also has relevance in a more general way, because it contains specific experiences over its historical trajectory that inform the plausibility of arguments from means more generally.

5.5 The wider problem with arguments from means

From the perspective of cognitive science as a discipline, there are three fundamental observations that complicate these arguments from means to attainment:

- (1) We don’t actually know how humans do what they do.
- (2) We don’t know the extent to which different means support high attainment.
- (3) However, we do know that different means can support the same attainment level.

Jointly, these observations limit the inferential strength of arguments from means to attainment in this context. Moreover, each of these observations is backed by a wealth of methodological experience, as well as specific

empirical evidence, within cognitive science -however surprising it may be outside of the discipline. To convey that, a brief history of cognitive science will suffice.

5.5.1 An Extremely Brief History of Cognitive Science. On the standard account, cognitive science was born as a response to behaviourism [114]. Behaviourism had sought to explain behaviour in terms of stimulus-response relationships without ‘looking into the black box’ of whatever internal cognitive processes might be mediating that connection. This proved too limiting an explanatory framework (though still one surprisingly powerful), in particular in domains that allowed wholly new, never-before produced, responses, such as language [25]. The cognitive revolution was then an attempt to develop a rigorous science of understanding that ‘black box’. To this end, it adopted the overarching framework of seeking to understand human cognition, and with it specific behaviours such as thinking or reasoning, in terms of information processing. That is, the project of cognitive science became trying to understand cognitive processing as computational.³

Two core insights from the history of cognitive science are important to the current topic. The first of these is David Marr’s insight that the explanation of computational systems requires explanations at multiple levels of explanation[79]. Three kinds of explanation are required to explain a computational device such as a cash register:

- (1) The computational level: a specification of the task the system is trying to solve and why. For a cash register this is addition, and the need to perform addition follows from our social and legal rules on purchase.
- (2) The algorithmic level: a specification of the algorithm the system is using to solve that task. For a cash register this is one of many possible algorithms for doing addition, such as carrying over the least significant digit.
- (3) The implementation level: a specification of the way the algorithm is realised in the physical device. For a cash register this is an understanding of transistors, logic gates and electrical flows etc.

The explanatory need for these three different levels follows from the fact that they are only loosely connected: For example there are different algorithms for addition, and any one of these could be physically realised in a multitude of ways (as is, in fact, the case with cash registers over the last century). Correspondingly, the three levels pick out very different aspects of the cash register and its relationship to the world.

Crucially, only when we have explanations of all three levels do we have a sufficient understanding of what a cash register is and does. Marr held that the same must apply for explanations of human cognition in information processing terms. In practice, understanding any one of these is so difficult when it comes to human cognition that most research in cognitive science is explicitly cast as addressing only one of these levels.

The second relevant insight from cognitive science is the recurring experience in the history of building computationally explicit models of human behaviour whereby initially very different types of models turned out to be empirically difficult, if not impossible, to distinguish. In other words, model mimicry, turned out to be an unexpected, but significant, empirical problem. Repeatedly, what looked like algorithmically opposing ideas turned out to have an unforeseen capacity to mirror each other’s predictions. This emerged in multiple different debates about otherwise unrelated cognitive phenomena. It also, arguably, led some of these formerly intense debates to simply fade away without ultimate resolution. A key example is the debate about mental imagery, which sought to understand the nature of the representations and processes underlying mental imagery such as imagining the mental rotation of an object and what it would look like from a different angle. Here, early, and intuitively compelling, empirical evidence supported some kind of pictorial representation; for example, the fact that it required more time to judge two images as rotated versions of the same object the further the physical rotation [116] or that more time was require for longer range scans across mental images [63] both

³This is not to be confused with the much narrower, and empirically implausible, idea that the human mind has a van Neumann architecture as underlies most computers.[28]

pointed toward an underlying analogue process of sorts. However, it proved extremely difficult to rule out rival propositional accounts that assumed language like, symbolic representations [98] (see on the history of the debate e.g.). Similarly, cognitive science saw periods of extensive debate about whether particular cognitive processes (e.g., attention [125] or memory retrieval [122]) involved serial or parallel processing, empirical debates that were made difficult by the fact that serial and parallel models could not only successfully mimic one another in common experimental paradigms, but also that entire classes of serial and parallel models turned out to be formally equivalent [124]. Yet a third debate plagued by such mimicry was the decades long attempt to distinguish between rule- versus similarity-based accounts of multiple cognitive processes, including reasoning and categorization [46].

5.5.2 The implications for arguments from means. As we just saw, it is in the nature of computational systems that many possible algorithms may perform the same computation and there are many possible implementations of the same algorithm. ‘Means’, as a dimension in the 3D organising space set out earlier, however, encompasses both algorithm and implementation.

And, crucially, for systems that involve meaningful degrees of self-organization or learning, ‘algorithms’ aren’t just the things we programmed directly. Understanding what the systems ‘does’ and how, even for the humble cash register, involves the need for intermediate and higher-level level functional descriptions. This is all the more the case for systems such as LLMs who function by identifying structure (statistical regularities) in their training data that allow them to fulfill the proximal task of next-token prediction.

This makes it *something to be discovered*, that is, an empirical question, whether a particular LLMs does something like ‘symbol processing’. Determining that is hard, and can give rise to borderline cases, but such empirical resolution has been the very business of cognitive science.

In keeping with this, there are active, programmes of research trying to address questions such as whether there is evidence of symbolic processing in LLMs [82, 136]. Such research is drawing on classic tools of cognitive science and the many techniques now merging into mechanistic interpretability research [111] which deliver practical tools for probing LLMs. At the same time, there is research seeking to develop new conceptual tools for understanding LLM functioning (e.g., [41]). In other words, understanding ‘the means’ by which LLMs attain their behaviour is a considerable research challenge in its own right and not something that can be read off simply from the code base underlying model training and generation of outputs.

By the same token, one cannot appeal simply to general characteristics of the system (‘does next token prediction’) and consider that to be a complete characterisation of ‘means’. Even less can one plausibly take such descriptions to exhaustively predict the kinds of algorithmic problems these systems may be able to tackle and with what precise level of competence.

In the absence of any knowledge about the history of cognitive science, doubting that we can infer reliably for these systems levels of attainment solely from an extremely partial understanding of their means might (understandably) come across simply as hand waving. Stating that we genuinely don’t know or can’t reliably infer levels of function simply from the fact that that these systems are based on next token prediction might be perceived as gesturing toward a mere logical possibility, that, in actual fact, is too remote to take seriously. The history of cognitive science, however, illustrates with multiple explicit examples how difficult inference from means to attainment is.

Finally, and crucially, none of the problems limiting inference from means to attainment illustrated by the history of cognitive science require any kind of endorsement of cognitive science as a discipline itself. There is continued, and substantial, criticism of the idea that human cognition might fruitfully be understood as computation or information processing [11, 59, 103, 114]. One can fully subscribe to those critiques and consider cognitive science a flawed and conceptually doomed endeavour. Such negative assessment, however, still leaves

the fundamental issues just identified wholly intact, and with that, the fundamental problem with arguments from means to attainment.

One can reject the theoretical framework of cognitive science, wholesale, but that just means we understand even less about human cognition than we might otherwise think. Such rejection leaves untouched the extensive experience cognitive science has made in exploring the connection between computational means and attainment remains. This is for the simple reason that, unlike human beings, generative AI systems undoubtedly *are* computational. So all of the fundamental experiences cognitive science has made with computational models of human performance remain directly applicable. The problem of model mimicry is a problem of computationally explicit systems mimicking each other when it comes to emulating human performance. Likewise, the need for multiple levels of explanation that arises because the computational, algorithmic, and implementation layer are only loosely connected is a core feature of computational devices.

In short, even if we abandon the notion of *human* cognition as computation, these issues still stand as features of computational processes themselves, and that genAI models are computational is not in doubt.

5.5.3 Arguments from means and reasoning. The upshot of the limitations of arguments from means in the context of LLMs is that arguments to the effect that LLMs are ‘not really reasoning’ based solely on computational means (e.g., ‘next token prediction’) are not compelling. There are too many examples involving computational systems that make clear not just that, but why, such inference is problematic.

It is important in this context to realise also that the weakness of such inference is something specific about computational systems and human tasks like ‘reasoning’. It is entirely possible in many cases to draw strong inferences about how things might behave on the basis of very general features only. One can know, for example, judge whether an object will float –for any object regardless of detail– solely from the weight of the volume of water it displaces. No further, detailed examination is required.

So there are many things for which we can confidently evaluate behaviour solely on the basis of some fundamental characteristic. It just so happens that ‘based on next token prediction’ is not (currently) that kind of characteristic. For prediction from fundamental features to relevant behaviour to work we need a causal connection between the feature and the behaviour of interest. That causal connection is currently lacking for the kinds of properties mooted as fundamental limitations.

Furthermore, a causal connection between properties such as ‘next token prediction’ or ‘not a human biological substrate’ is not just exactly what we are missing, we have found ourselves, historically, in the position of exploring the implications of those properties precisely because we do not understand what brings about human reasoning in the first place. Hence, denying attainment on the basis of these particular means seems question begging.

It is also not the case that we cannot draw robust attainment inferences from these particular means because we are dealing specifically with computational systems. Computational complexity theory, in effect, formally characterises strong attainment implications for entire classes of algorithms by identifying how resource needs such as run time to completion develop as a function of the size of the input problem [32]. Such analyses show that many some problems are not amenable to a particular algorithmic solution in any practical sense. Such an approach can also be applied to large language models, and the work of van Rooij et al. [130] attempts to do just that by seeking to demonstrate that ‘Artificial General Intelligence’ (AGI), and, by that, human level reasoning attainment, is not something that can be learned from data on standard notions of practically feasible computation as developed by computational complexity theory.

Their elegant proof demonstrates the (practical) impossibility of mastering the following learning problem: the algorithm receives pairs of situations and human responses (behaviours) to those situations as inputs (or data) and must learn to produce accurate human responses to these and to new situations. Of the possible set of

behaviours for each situation, the algorithm simply has to select one such behaviour at levels “non-negligibly better than chance”.

The proof manages to demonstrate this without appealing to any details of how a learner might do this. The result does not require the specification of an algorithm, so holds *regardless of what algorithmic means are chosen*, making the proof extremely powerful.

The fundamental problem with the proof, however, lies in the way it defines the attainment target. AGI is a term that has crept into the AI literature only rather recently, and its meaning is itself under debate. [18] define it as follows:

“We use AGI to refer to systems that demonstrate broad capabilities of intelligence, including reasoning, planning, and the ability to learn from experience, and with these capabilities at or above human-level” (Bubeck et al., 2023, pg. 4)

What van Rooij et al.’s proof shows is that the problem of learning to *match human behaviour* –where ‘behaviour’ is defined as a finite distribution of situation-response pairs– cannot be learned by brute force.

In other words, we can’t machine learn our way to a general human behaviour prediction machine. That result, and with it the proof, is clearly of significant interest to anyone interested in scientifically understanding human behaviour, but it is at odds with the stated goals of AGI. As the quote indicates, the aim, there, is not to build a system that directly matches human responding; instead, it is not just acceptable, but in fact likely desired, that the system could perform *better* than humans on some tasks.

In other words, the goal is to build a system capable of ‘reasoning’, not a system that provides answers that match actual human responses. Actual human reasoning is rife with bias and error, and where LLMs produce similar mistakes that is not seen as a triumph, but as a problem [74] that undermines the real-world utility of these systems (albeit not their interest for cognitive science). Consequently, the proof is simply aimed at a different attainment target and that limits its applicability.

Of course, comparison to human performance is an integral part of evaluating the attainment of LLMs –as has historically been the case with other AI systems– but it has not generally been the goal of AI research, per se, to build a human mimicry machine. The Turing test has a long history as a putative operational metric for assessing AI [39], but it is important, here as elsewhere, not to confuse a metric with the goal. Most systems in the history of AI have not even had the capabilities to participate in the Turing test, but nobody thought them the worse for it: it was not the point of Deep Blue [22] to converse with Gary Kasparov, nor was it the point of Deep Blue to play chess like Gary Kasparov, the point was to beat him at chess. LLMs confuse this picture because they are deployed to be conversational, but that shouldn’t obscure the fundamental point that the goal of creating an artificial system capable of reasoning is not the same thing as creating a system that mimics human responses, and empirical evaluations of the reasoning performance of large language models make that clear.

We could, of course, choose to *define* ‘reasoning’ by actual human observed attainment, thus limiting the term ‘reasoning’ to only those systems that produce outputs sufficiently close to actual human answers on reasoning tasks. This will exclude, by definition, any ‘reasoning’ systems AI has created to date, as it will any possibility of ‘reasoning’ in other, non-human species [21]. It also seems strangely at odds with the fact that human reasoning performance is, in many ways, not fixed. Over the course of human history, we have developed numerous practical and conceptual tools to improve reasoning; the formal tools that make up our normative theories of rationality, that is, logic, probability theory and decision theory, are but one example [45], and we continue to devote substantial effort to improving critical thinking in a myriad of ways [1, 44, 105].

In conclusion then, the limitations of arguments from means to attainment in the context of reasoning stem not from the fact that such arguments could never be compelling, but from the fact that the underlying means of the specific target task ‘reasoning’ are too poorly understood.

5.6 Other arguments against reasoning in LLMs

There are further arguments that have been put forward against the notion that LLMs reason. One of these is the argument that LLMs lack rationality [123], in keeping with philosophical perspectives on the construal of the term (for an indication of what rigorous empirical tests of this hypothesis might look like, see [9]). Another is the idea that LLMs lack agency [20, 58]. There will likely be more. As it is not the goal of this paper to decide the question of whether LLMs reason, but rather to illuminate the debate, it suffices here to say that arguments based on rationality or on agency, when examined in detail, will likely recapitulate many of the issues already discussed. Both rationality and agency are concepts that admit of more or less, which complicates finding non-arbitrary boundaries.

In the case of rationality, actual humans are clearly a mix of rational and irrational and that includes the context of reasoning. Furthermore, it has proved challenging in the psychology of reasoning (as well as in judgment and decision-making research) to evaluate the rationality of human performance, last but not least, because answers that seemingly violate rationality norms, often, on closer inspection can be reconstructed as nevertheless rational under slightly different assumptions. All of this makes the question of how much, precisely, behaviour of LLMs would have to align with common conceptions of rationality a very real one. Likewise, agency is itself a highly contested notion (see [112]), in particular regarding potential non-human agents.

Furthermore, the notions of rationality and the notion of agency are, arguably, themselves bound up with each other, meaning that adjustments we make to the individual concepts of ‘reasoning’, ‘rationality’, or ‘agency’ may impact the others that exist in a network of inter-related notions trying to capture core aspects of human nature and human behaviour. It seems typical of reflection on core aspects of human behaviour and human nature that our networks of relevant concepts seem clear only as long as they are not pushed. The existence of non-human systems with non-trivial levels of attainment on seemingly human tasks will necessarily exert such a push. Rather than admitting of clean, simple answers, it seems more likely that the existence of LLMs will prompt change and further development of our understanding of the entire network of those concepts themselves.

6 Does all this matter?

Before concluding, it seems important to re-situate this debate about whether LLMs reason in the wider context of the development and societal impact of these systems. It’s not coincidental that some of the most negative verdicts on whether LLMs ‘reason’ come from authors who are cautioning against their adoption. And there are many compelling reasons for that caution ranging from the epistemic degradation of our environment, through the possibility of uncontrolled economic damage, to the fact that any increase in energy use is concerning at this pivotal moment with respect to climate change.

So seeking to clarify whether LLMs reason may seem like an arcane (and somewhat irresponsible) debate in the context of the real societal impact of these models. It might even be seen as an endorsement of the current development and adoption of genAI or an undermining of attempts to counter those societal developments.

That is very much not the intention of this paper. This paper is about clarifying an important concept (‘reasoning’). That concept has a central role in a controversial debate. That debate matters because generative AI matters, but the concept of reasoning itself matters well beyond that debate. If nothing else, ‘reason’ (ratio) and ‘reasoning’ are concepts that have been at the heart of debate about what it means to be human for millenia. They feature in important ways not just in the disciplines and contexts discussed in this article, but in many others.

For the same reasons, it seems likely that the very existence of these systems will change our concepts and change our understanding of tasks such as ‘reasoning’, precisely because they are non-human systems seeking to compete in a previously human arena. Against that background, the purpose of this paper is not to legislate usage, but simply to bring greater clarity to any such development.

7 Conclusions

This paper has sought to clarify terminological and conceptual confusion that obscures current debate about whether large-language models ‘reason’. The paper identified the close conceptual and empirical interplay between the characterisation of a task, the means for accompanying it, and the resultant levels of attainment as an added difficulty when it comes to determining category boundaries for behaviour terms. It surveyed usage of the term ‘reasoning’ *prior* to the rise of large language models both in everyday use and across three disciplines -psychology, AI, and philosophy.

It then used the distinction between task, means, and attainment as a framework for clarifying meaning relevant aspects and inferential relationships in such a way as to allow one to pin-point fundamental disciplinary differences in the way the term ‘reasoning’ is used. This analysis demonstrates also that other disciplinary perspectives are at odds with the main discipline that studies ‘reasoning’ empirically (i.e., psychology).

It then argued that familiarity with the nature of computational explanation within cognitive science, as well as the recurring experience within that field of unexpected model mimicry, modulate perceptions of the extent to which characterisations of means are likely constraining of LLM attainment. Specifically, it is argued that the persuasive power of arguments in the current literature that deny any possibility of reasoning on the basis of characteristics means is considerably diminished once the one-to-many relationships typically involved in illuminating the nature of computational processes is recognised. To that end, cognitive science offers not just theoretical constructs (such as Marr’s levels of explanation [79]) but a now seven decade history with numerous examples.

All of this debate could be re-run for specific kinds of reasoning: logical reasoning, causal reasoning, explanatory reasoning, probabilistic reasoning, mathematical reasoning, analogical reasoning, moral reasoning, case-based reasoning, default reasoning and so on. This suggests that greater clarity on the issues confounding debate about reasoning in LLMs is important.

In short, the paper has sought to demonstrate why the question of whether or not LLMs reason has no simple, obvious, answer and why analyses may genuinely, and reasonably, disagree. Conceptions of ‘reasoning’ are neither sufficiently precise or agreed-upon to allow a simple universal answer. Instead, the context and function of the classification decision will have significant impact in any verdict (see also [137]). At the same time, the existence of LLMs themselves will likely end up changing our conceptions. Either way, it is hoped that a better understanding of extant divergence and ambiguities will allow more fruitful discussion and better conceptual and terminological clarification.

Acknowledgments

This article draws on early sketches of some of the ideas developed in two blog posts (at: <https://write.as/ulrikehahn/do-llms-really-reason-understand-think-summarise> and <https://write.as/ulrikehahn/stochastic-parrot-is-a-misleading-metaphor-for-llms>) as well as a talk at the workshop “Reasoning Across Minds and Machines” at the 2025 Annual Meeting of the Cognitive Science Society.

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